

ISic0231

Epitaph of Vecilia

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Thermae Himeraeae

Place of origin (modern)

Termini Imerese

Provenance

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Termini Imerese, Museo Civico Baldassare Romano, inventory 3

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Vecilia

2. ave

Apparatus

Text from autopsy and photograph

Bivona reads D M above line 1, but this appears to be a highly optimistic interpretation of various marks on the stone

Translation (en)

Vecilia, hail!

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 175704

EDR 077926

EDCS 8900404

Bibliography

1888-. L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. *L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine..* At 1980.0526

Bivona, L. 1994. Iscrizioni latine lapidarie del museo civico di Termini Imerese. *Kokalos Supplementi / Sikelika serie storica*. Palermo / Rome. At 156

Bivona, L 1975-1976. Nuove iscrizioni di Termini Imerese (Palermo). *Atti della Accademia di Scienze, Lettere e Arti di Palermo*. Ser.4, vol.35: 531-558. At 550 no.14 tav.7

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